

Feasibility of hybridization between *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) and *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Motsch.) in rice

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To test the feasibility of interspecific hybridization between *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) and *Nephotettix nigropictus* (Motsch.), green (NVGR) and blue (NVBR) forms of *N. virescens* were separately reared on TN1 rice plants (R) for six generations. *N. nigropictus* individuals, originally collected from ricefield bunds, were reared and maintained separately on grass *Echinochloa colona* (E) (NNGE) and on rice cultivar TN1 (NNGR) for five generations. Attempts were made to hybridize blue (NVBRF) and green (NVGRF) females of *N. virescens* with green males of *N. nigropictus* reared on *E. colona* (NNGEM) separately. Crosses of blue females of *N. virescens* (NVBRF) and *N. nigropictus* green males raised on TN1 (NNGRM) were also made. Intraspecific crosses between NVBRF and green *N. virescens* males (NVGRM) were made to estimate the normal fertility levels between the two forms. Studies were replicated four times. The ability of NNGE, NNGR, NVBR, NVGR, and the interspecific hybrids of NVBRF/

Table 1. Interspecific crosses between *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus*^a.

Cross ^b	Eggs		Nymphs emerged (no.)	Nymphs surviving to adult stage (no.)	Survival up to adult stage (%)
	Fertile (no.)	Infertile (no.)			
NVBRF/NNGEM	2.2 ± 0.6	26.0 ± 2.12	0.0	0.0	0.0
NVGRF/NNGEM	3.6 ± 0.7	54.0 ± 3.81	0.0	0.0	0.0
NVBRF/NNGRM	- ^c	-	56.5 ± 4.62	26.5 ± 3.72	46.25 ± 3.25
NVBRM/NNGRF	-	-	48.75 ± 3.54	20.0 ± 1.66	40.5 ± 1.81
NVBRF/NVGRM	-	-	-	46.4 ± 14.9	-

^aMean ± SEM of 4 replications. ^bNVBRF = *N. virescens* blue female on rice, NNGEM = *N. nigropictus* green male on *E. colona*, NVGRF = *N. virescens* green female on rice, NNGRM = *N. nigropictus* green male on rice, NVBRM = *N. virescens* blue male on rice, NNGRF = *N. nigropictus* green female on rice, and NVGRM = *N. virescens* green male on rice. ^cObservations not recorded.

Table 2. Rice tungro disease transmission by *Nephotettix* spp.^a

<i>Nephotettix</i> spp., strain or hybrids ^b	Transmitters (%)	
	Female	Male
NVGR	33.3 b	73.3 b
NVBR	66.6 a	80.0 a
NNGR	11.1 d	27.2 d
NNGE	23.3 c	26.6 d
NVBRF/NNGRM	34.9 b	38.1 c
NNGRF/NVBRM	28.9 bc	41.0 c

^aMean ± SEM of 3 replications. The values in a column followed by the same letter are not significantly different at P = 0.05 according to LSD method. ^bNVGR = green *N. virescens* on rice, NVBR = blue *N. virescens* on rice, NNGR = green *N. nigropictus* on rice, NNGE = green *N. nigropictus* on *E. colona*, NVBRF = *N. virescens* blue female on rice, NNGRM = *N. nigropictus* green male on rice, NNGRF = *N. nigropictus* green female on rice, and NVBRM = *N. virescens* blue male on rice.

NNGRM and NNGRF/NVBRM to transmit rice tungro disease (RTD) was also tested in three replications.

No nymphs were produced by crosses between NVBRF or NVGRF and NNGEM, although a few fertile eggs

were laid, as determined by eyespot development (Table 1). In contrast, crosses between NVBRF and NNGRM produced many nymphs, almost half of which survived to the adult stage. The reciprocal cross between NVBRM and NNGRF also produced a large proportion of nymphs that survived to the adult stage. Thus, the success of interspecific crosses between *N. virescens* and *N. nigropictus* appears to depend in part on whether *N. nigropictus* has been reared on rice.

The individuals of NNGE and NNGR transmitted RTD but less efficiently than did NVBR and NVGR forms. The transmission ability of the interspecific hybrids of NVBRF/NNGRM and NNGRF/NVBRM was of intermediate order (Table 2).

We are currently studying the level of fertility in the F₂ generation of interspecific hybrids and their ability to transmit RTD. ■

Integrated pest management — weeds

Rice off-types in Central Luzon, Philippines

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A ricefield survey was conducted every 100 m along the main roads within 10-km radii of PhilRice, Muñoz, Nueva Ecija; Guimba, Nueva Ecija; and Victoria, Tarlac, Philippines, for off-types from 4 Oct to 4 Nov 1993. We surveyed 1,917 fields. Mature panicles were collected from 44 fields and brought to IRRI for further characterization.

The off-types were taller than the cultivated varieties, had different grain

characteristics, and tended to lodge. They were separated into two groups based on hull color: straw and black. One hundred and two (5.3%) of the fields were infested with black-hulled off-types while 187 (9.8%) were infested with straw-colored off-types. The highest level of infestation was 30% for the black-hulled off-types in a field 8.4 km from the Victoria Municipal Hall on the Victoria-Tarlac road and 20% for the straw-hulled off-type in a field 1.4 km from the Guimba Municipal Hall on the Guimba-Victoria road. Two hundred and twenty-four panicles were collected. Of

these, 89 were from cultivated rice, 75 from black-hulled off-types, and 60 from straw-colored off-types.

The cultivated varieties had more panicles per plant, less grains per panicle, and narrower and longer grains than the off-types (see figure). Grain weight was similar for the cultivated varieties and the off-types. The grains of the black-hulled off-types were bolder than those of the straw-hulled off-types. Most of the grains were awnless or had short awns. Most awns were observed in the black-hulled off-type grains with 30.4% having awns greater than 2.0 cm in length.